

SOIL IMPROVEMENT USING LIME AND POLYPROPYLENE FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

Soil modification is the process which involves enhancing the anatomical substance of the soil apropos improve its strength, durability by mixing with additives. Foundation of a structure on the soft clay soil may be responsible for the excessive settlement of the structure. Soil modification helps to decreasing the foundation cost by increasing bearing capacity. In this study, lime and polypropylene fibres were used with soil to observe its effect on the bearing capacity. Different concentration of lime (0 to 15%) by weight of soil and 2% polypropylene fibres by weight of lime were mixed with different soil samples according to the soil categories like sandy and clay and silt soil. The necessary parameters of the soil were determined and unconfined compressive strength of the soil was also measured by laboratory testing machine with different curing days. The result revealed the optimum value of the unconfined compressive strength was obtained for the concentration of 10% lime for clay and silt soil on the other hand 7.5% for the sandy soil.

KEYWORD: Soil Improvement, Unconfined Compressive Strength, Lime, polypropylene fibres.

INTRODUCTION

Soil enhancement is the term of permanent solution by the originally and chemically improvement of soil properties. Implementation of earth increase the bearing capacity of the soil beside it's reduce the settlement of the foundation and control the shrink-swell of the soils. Stabilization of soil can be used to treat a wide range of sub-grade materials from expansive clays. There are various way to improve the subsoil which is very soft and expansive in the geotechnical field by using the different materials, like polypropylene fibres. The improvement of sub-structure, Pavement, roadways, building foundations, channel and reservoir linings, irrigation systems, water lines, and at sewer lines to avoid the damage due to the settlement of the soft soil or to the swelling action of the expansive soils. Requisite to develop by the chemical stabilization at the soft fine-grained soil. Chemical stabilization wind up mixing chemical additives with natural soils to remove moisture and increase strength of the soil especially in the sectors sub-grade. The stabilizing materials in the treatment process is either reinforcing of the bonds between the particles or filling of the pore spaces.

Chemically soil stabilization is achieved by the addition of proper percentages of cement, lime, fly ash, bitumen, or combinations of these materials to the soil. Alternative of the type and the determination of the concentration of the additive were used are dependent over the soil classification and the rate of improvement in soil quality desired. Mostly, little amounts of additives are required when it is simply desired to modify soil substance what gradation, workability, and plasticity. When it is term to improve the strength and durability respectively, bigger quantities of additive are used. After the additive has been mixed with soil, spreading and compaction are achieved by conventional means. It is a great chance to make settlement at foundation and basement with the changes of moisture content because moisture in the soil changes expansive soil will move. In the time of wetter clay grows, during dry seasons clay shrinks.

Santoni et al (2001), studied on six types of non-plastic cohesion less soils reinforced with monofilament polypropylene fiber the unconfined compressive strength of reinforced soil. They found optimum fiber

content is 0.8% and fiber content is less than 0.6% caused strain softening more than 0.85% causes strain hardening. *Kumar, Walia and Bajaj* (2007), have reinforced the black cotton soil with polyester synthetic. They investigated on unconfined compressive fly ash, lime and randomly oriented fibers on the characteristics of expansive soils. The results shows that unconfined compressive strength increases with increase of fiber content. *Chandra et la* (2008), have studied on three types of soil reinforced with polypropylene fiber of 0.3mm diameter the static triaxial test of unreinforced and reinforced soil shows that uniaxial compressive strength for lower value is 3.824 and optimum value is 9.712 MPa respectively. (1979), *Andersland and khattak* made a research on the kaolinite soil with the cellulose fiber fibers. The triaxial test was conducted the test results indicates the addition of fiber at 16% increase the maximum shear strength by 43% when the pure kaolinite is used. (1983), *Gray and Ohashi* were perform an extensive study on the shear strength of the soil reinforced with fibers and they concluded the inclusion of fibers in sands increases peak shear strength and limited post peak decrease in shear resistance. (1987), *Setty and Rao* have investigated on lateritic soil at optimum moisture content and reinforcement with polypropylene fiber. The triaxial test, CBR and tensile test are conducted the results indicated that the addition of fibers increases cohesion and slightly decreases Φ and also showed that CBR value has been improved by 2.2 times up to 2% fiber content and also improves dry strength. *Ranjan et al* (1996), studied on different types of soils likewise sand, medium sand, fine sand, silt sand and silt reinforced with polypropylene monofilament coir and bhabar the result of triaxial test showed greater ductility, no loss of post peak strength and increase in stiffness. Due to tensile strength in fibers confining pressure is greater than critical confining pressure. *Charan* (1996), studied on silt, sand to coarse sand reinforced with polypropylene and natural fiber coir and bhabar the triaxial and CBR test were conducted the test results shows that the confining pressure is less than critical confining pressure and the CBR value is improved by two times at the fiber of 1.5%.

OBJECTIVE OF THIS STUDY

Bangladesh is full of resource because of its riverine. Bangladesh is country with pre-dominantly alluvial soil. Because of existence of high water table, in most cases, throughout the year the soil remains wet or saturated with water. In such a situation, engineers often have to go for costly foundation in constructing roads and buildings. Sub grade soil with a CBR value of less than 3 or SPT value of 2 or 3 often encountered in the field. When the SPT value is 2 or less, engineers are often forced to go for deep foundation even for low rise three to four story building. By improving the strength of sub grade soil, cost of road and building construction can be reduced effectively. Previous studies have revealed that lime and fiber added with soil can improve the bearing capacity of soil. This study is aimed at assessing the Improvement of bearing capacity of local soil by using lime and locally available polypropylene fiber in different proportions. If significant improvement is observed with the local soil then findings may be used by the practicing engineers for designing and ensuring economy in construction.

METHODOLOGY

The soil sample collected from different part of Dhaka city especially from the Aftab Nagor and Narayanganj area. These soil samples were classified according to Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) classification. Atterberg limit test, sieve analysis as well as Hydrometer Analysis were conducted. The consistency limit test of soil by using the Casagrande apparatus. The ASTM standard procedure was followed for performing particle-size analysis of fine grinded soil that was based on the sedimentation of the particle, and was measured by flotation of hydrometer for 36 hours. Lime slurry can be used to exercise soils which is made by chemically change calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) into calcium oxide beside hydrated lime is drawn up when quicklime chemically operate together with water. Locally available limestone was collected from the market. The limestone was converted into powder by drop a little bit of water.

Lime and polypropylene fiber has been added to test the improvement in stabilization of the soil samples. There curing periods: 0, 3, 7, 14, 21 and 28 days were used. Nine different percentages of lime: 0%, 2.5%, 5%, 7.5%, 10%, 12.5%, and 15% were used. It was mixed with a constant 2% nylon thread by weight of

lime. The compressive strengths of lime stabilized soil were evaluated for different curing period: 3, 7, 14, 21, and 28 days.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Soil Properties (Flat land soil Aftab Nagor, Dhaka)							
According to MIT soil classification, this soil is sandy silt and some clay.							
Parameters	Percentages (%)	Concentration of lime (%)	Compressive strength (psi)				
			3days	7days	14days	21days	28days
Sand	20	0	8	8	8	8	8
Silt	65	2.5	15	22	27	32	33
Clay	15	5	18	27	36	31	42
Liquid limit	27	7.5	18	30	37	46	50
Plastic limit	15	10	26	32	40	50	57
Plasticity index	12	12.5	22	35	38	48	54
Optimum Moisture content	19	15	20	24	21	36	37
Specific gravity	2.65	0 Control specimen Average value compressive strength 2% polypropylene fibres by weight of lime					
Salinity	Nil						

Unconfined compressive strength of flat soil with varying percentages of lime and various curing period.

Unconfined compressive strength of field soil with varying percentages of lime and various curing period.

The result be associated with the classification of soil samples of soil sample are shown in the tabular form.

Soil Properties (fields soil from Narayanganj, Dhaka)

According to MIT soil classification, this soil is clayey, silt and some sand.							
Parameters	Percentages (%)	Concentration of lime (%)	Compressive strength (psi)				
			3days	7days	14days	21days	28days
Sand	15	0	7	7	7	7	7
Silt	25	2.5	10	14	17	20	23
Clay	60	5	11	18	21	27	29
Optimum moisture content	19	7.5	17	22	30	30	37
Specific gravity	2.6	10	17	18	28	30	35
Salinity	Nil	12.5	14	17	28	23	32
		15	9	16	21	28	30

*** 0 Control specimen**
Average value compressive strength
2% polypropylene fibres by weight of lime

The concentration of limestone procedures are given as follows from the local market.

Lime properties		
No	Concentrations %	Parameters
1	70	Calcium oxid-CaO
2	30	Additive materials

CONCLUSION

The result stated which the optimum value of the unconfined compressive strength was obtained for the concentration of 10% lime with addition of 2% polypropylene fibers by the weight of lime for clay and silt soil on the other hand 7.5% with 2% polypropylene fibers by the weight of lime for the sandy soil. The increase is more than many times from the base strength of the normal soil. It is also noticeable that when the percentage of sand increase the strength decrease for the reason of the run-on of lime and polypropylene fibres in the earth. The bearing capacity increase with curing time.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thankfully acknowledges the services given by the laboratory technicians of the Bangladesh university engineering and technology, (BUET) Geotechnical laboratory during the experiments. We also thankful to Eng. S.M.Tanjid Ahmed for his all kinds of support.

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